

Niementowski 4-Ketoquinazoline Synthesis: Modification and Mechanism (Part II). Synthesis of 5,6,7 and 8-Chloro-2(R)-3(H)-4-Ketoquinazolines

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The modified Niementowski 4-ketoquinazoline synthesis comprising condensation of an N-acyl anthranilic acid with formamide has been applied in the synthesis of 5, 6, 7 and 8-chloro-2(R)-3(H)-4-ketoquinazolines. The results obtained have been interpreted on the basis of the proposed reaction-mechanism¹.

In an earlier communication¹, the authors described syntheses of various 2-substituted-4-ketoquinazolines by the modified Niementowski-4-ketoquinazoline synthesis comprising condensation of a suitable N-acyl anthranilic acid with formamide. The present communication deals with the study of the application of this modified reaction in the synthesis of benzene-chlorine substituted-2(R)-3(H)-4-ketoquinazolines.

The modified Niementowski synthesis between a chlorine substituted N-acyl anthranilic acid and formamide was effected at various temperatures ranging from 150 to 240°. The molar proportion of formamide used per mole of the N-acyl anthranilic acid varied from one mole to three moles. But much larger molar proportions of formamide had to be used in case of the highly insoluble chlorine substituted N-acyl, particularly N-*p*-nitrobenzoyl anthranilic acids. Smaller amount of formamide was used with a view to isolating if possible, chlorine substituted N-acyl anthranilamide, which is believed to be an intermediate in the Niementowski 4-ketoquinazoline synthesis¹.

4,5 and 6-chloro-N-acyl anthranilic acids required here (listed in table I) were synthesised starting with the corresponding chlorine substituted *o*-toluidine derivatives. The latter was N-acylated and subsequently oxidised by neutral aqueous permanganate solution to the corresponding N-acyl anthranilic acid. Oxidation of some N-acyl-*o*-toluidine derivatives remained incomplete because of their very low solubility. The corresponding N-acyl anthranilic acid was prepared by N-acylation of the appropriate anthranilic acid; the latter was formed on hydrolysis of the corresponding N-acetyl anthranilic acid. 3-Chloro-N-acyl anthranilic acids were synthesised following the method described by Chaudhari and Nargund².

3-Chloro-N-acetyl and N-benzoyl anthranilic acids on condensation with formamide at 160° yielded 2-methyl and 2-phenyl-3(H)-8-chloro-4-ketoquinazolines in 70% and 62% yield respectively. 2-Methyl and 2-phenyl-3(H)-5-chloro-4-ketoquinazolines were formed in 68 and 60% yields respectively on condensing 6-chloro-N-acetyl and N-benzoyl anthranilic acids respectively with formamide at 160° and 180°.

1. V. S. Patel and S. R. Patel, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **42**, 531.
2. M. B. Chaudhari and K. S. Nargund, *J. Univ. Bombay*, 1950, **28**, 65.

5-Chloro-N-acetyl anthranilic acid when condensed with formamide at 150° yielded 2-methyl-3(H)-6-chloro-4-ketoquinazoline in 78% yield. The latter was formed in very poor yield when prepared by the original Niementowski 4-ketoquinazoline synthesis comprising a condensation between 5-chloro anthranilic acid and acetamide at 200°; higher reaction-temperature was required as at lower temperature the reaction proceeded to a very small extent even when the reaction period was increased to five to six hours. It has been reported by other workers that higher temperature and longer heating periods are required for the condensation of bz-substituted anthranilic acids and for higher acidamides in the Niementowski 4-ketoquinazoline synthesis³. 2-Phenyl, 2-*p*-nitrophenyl and 2-*p*-anisyl-3(H)-6-chloro-4-ketoquinazolines were formed in 66, 66 and 55% yields respectively when 5-chloro-N-benzoyl, N-*p*-nitrobenzoyl and N-*p*-anisoyl anthranilic acids were condensed respectively with formamide at temperatures nearing 200°.

Condensation of 5-Chloro-N-*o*-chlorobenzoyl anthranilic acid with formamide was studied at different temperatures with a view to isolating if possible, the intermediate 5-Chloro-N-*o*-chlorobenzoyl anthranilamide(I). Because of the presence of the *o*-chlorine atom in the N-royl group the latter may be expected to be cyclodehydrated with difficulty⁴. At lower temperature there was no reaction but at higher temperature the product obtained seemed to be a mixture of the expected compound viz., 2-*o*-chlorophenyl-3(H)-6-chloro-4-ketoquinazoline (II) and its precursor 5-chloro anthranilamide derivative(I). It was not possible to effect the separation of this mixture by repeated crystallisations. But the mixture could be quantitatively transformed into (II) on treatment with hot dilute alkali solution. It has been reported by the present authors that N-*o*-chlorobenzoyl anthranilic acid on condensation with formamide furnished N-*o*-chlorobenzoyl anthranilamide.¹

Condensation of 4-Chloro-N-acetyl anthranilic acid with formamide at 160° yielded 2-methyl-3(H)-7-chloro-4-ketoquinazoline in 79% yield. 2-Phenyl, 2-*p*-nitrophenyl and 2-*p*-anisyl-3(H)-7-chloro-4-ketoquinazolines were formed in 65, 61 and 55% yield by condensing 4-chloro-N-benzoyl, N-*p*-nitrobenzoyl and N-*p*-anisoyl anthranilic acids respectively with formamide at temperatures nearing 200°. The condensation of 4-Chloro-N-*o*-chlorobenzoyl anthranilic acid with formamide at 190° afforded a product which seemed to be a mixture of 4-chloro-N-*o*-chlorobenzoyl-anthranilamide and 2-*o*-chlorophenyl-3(H)-7-chloro-4-ketoquinazoline(III). This product was transformed almost completely into (III) on treatment with hot dilute alkali solution.

The results of this study indicate that the modified Niementowski 4-ketoquinazoline synthesis has proved successful in the synthesis of bz-chlorine substituted-2-alkyl and 2-aryl-3(H)-4-ketoquinazolines; the product obtained was pure and the reaction could be carried out at a comparatively lower temperature and in short time. No decarboxylation had been observed. The second point worth noting is that the yields of the corresponding 5,6,7 and 8-chloro-2(R)-substituted-3(H)-4-ketoquinazolines are almost the same irrespective of the position of the chlorine atom in the chlorine substituted N-acyl(R-CO)-anthranilic acid.

3. L. Sherrill Mary and Co-workers, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, **68**, 1299, 1301.

4. D. T. Zentmyer and E. C. Wagner, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1949, **14**, 967.

EXPERIMENTAL

(A) *Oxidation of chlorine substituted N-acyl-o-toluidide: Formation of chlorine substituted N-acyl anthranilic acid (method—1):* Finely powdered chlorine substituted-*o*-N-acyl toluide (3 g) was suspended in a solution of potassium permanganate (4 g) and magnesium sulphate (3 g) in water (125 ml) and heated on a water bath with a vigorous mechanical stirring till the permanganate colour disappeared. The reaction mixture was filtered hot to remove manganese dioxide. The latter was washed with boiling water. The filtrate and the washings were mixed and concentrated to a bulk of about 60 ml. The concentrated solution was cooled and acidified. The white crystalline solid which separated out was filtered and washed. It was crystallised from dilute alcohol in white long needles. The chlorine substituted N-acyl anthranilic acids thus prepared have been listed in the table I).

TABLE I

Chlorine substituted N-acyl anthranilic acid

No.	Chlorine substituted N-acyl anthranilic acid	M.P. °C	Formula	%Nitrogen		Ref. No.
				Found	Reqd.	
1.*	3-Chloro-N-acetyl anthranilic acid	196	C ₉ H ₈ NO ₃ Cl	6.4	6.5	
2.*	3-Chloro-N-benzoyl anthranilic acid	184-85	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ NO ₃ Cl	5.2	5.1	
3.	6-Chloro-N-acetyl anthranilic acid	215	C ₉ H ₈ NO ₃ Cl	6.3	6.5	6
4.	6-Chloro-N-benzoyl anthranilic acid	185-86	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ NO ₃ Cl	4.9	5.1	
5.	5-Chloro-N-acetyl anthranilic acid	203-4	C ₉ H ₈ NO ₃ Cl	6.4	6.5	5,7
6.*	5-Chloro-N-benzoyl anthranilic acid	196-97	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ NO ₃ Cl	5.3	5.1	
7.*	5-Chloro-N- <i>p</i> -nitro benzoyl anthranilic acid	256-57	C ₁₄ H ₉ N ₂ O ₅ Cl	8.6	8.7	
8.*	5-Chloro-N- <i>p</i> -anisoyl anthranilic acid	245-46	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ NO ₄ Cl	4.5	4.6	
9.*	5-Chloro-N- <i>o</i> -chloro benzoyl anthranilic acid	228-29	C ₁₄ H ₉ NO ₃ Cl ₂	4.6	4.5	
10.	4-Chloro-N-acetyl anthranilic acid	214	C ₉ H ₈ NO ₃ Cl	6.5	6.5	6
11.*	4-Chloro-N-benzoyl anthranilic acid	223	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ NO ₃ Cl	5.1	5.1	8,9
12.*	4-Chloro-N- <i>p</i> -nitro benzoyl anthranilic acid	256-57	C ₁₄ H ₉ N ₂ O ₅ Cl	8.8	8.7	
13.*	4-Chloro-N- <i>p</i> -anisoyl anthranilic acid	225-26	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ NO ₄ Cl	4.7	4.6	
14.*	4-Chloro-N- <i>o</i> -chloro benzoyl anthranilic acid	211-12	C ₁₄ H ₉ NO ₃ Cl ₂	4.4	4.5	

*These acids were prepared by method-2 and the rest were prepared by method-1.

(B) *Hydrolysis of chlorine substituted N-acyl anthranilic acid: Formation of chloro anthranilic acid:* A mixture of chlorine substituted-N-acetyl anthranilic acid (10 g) and HCl acid (1:1, 100 ml) was heated on a water bath for about two hours. The clear solution was then made just alkaline by adding a soln. of aq. NaOH. The cooled solution when made just acidic by adding the required amount of AcOH furnished a white product. It was filtered, washed, dried and crystallised from hot water in white needles.

(C) *N-acyl anthranilic acid (Method-2):* It was obtained by refluxing a mixture of chlorine substituted anthranilic acid (0.01 mole), substituted aroylchloride (0.012-mole) in dry benzene (30 ml.) containing a drop of pyridine, for four hours. The reaction mixture was cooled and the solid product was collected and washed with hot water. It was crystallised from alcohol.

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7. D. R. P. Hochster Farbw., 152484; *Chem. Zentr.*, 1904, **2**, 168.
8. J. V. Hunn, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, **45**, 1028.
9. G. Heller and L. Hessel, *J. prakt. chem.*, 1928, **2**, 120, 64-73.

(D) *Modified Niementowski-4-ketoquinazoline synthesis*: Chlorine substituted-N-acyl (R-CO) anthranilic acid (1 mole) and formamide (1 to 3 moles for R=alkyl, 1 to 5 moles for R=Ph, 1 to 10 moles for R=*p*-nitrophenyl and *o*-chlorophenyl) were heated together at about 200° for two hours. The cooled reaction mass was powdered and suspended and stirred in bicarbonate solution. The solid was filtered and washed with water. It was crystallised from acetic acid. The compounds prepared by this method have been listed in table II.

TABLE II

Bz-chlorine-substituted-2(R)-3(H)-4-ketoquinazoline

R	R'	Ob- tained from Cl-N- acyl anthra- nilic acid	Moles of HCONH ₂ per mole of A.A.	Reaction Temp. °C	Yield %	M.P. °C	Formula	%Nitrogen Found Reqd.		Ref. No.
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
Me	8-Cl	1	3	160	70	247	C ₉ H ₇ N ₂ OCl	14.7	14.4	
Ph	8-Cl	2	7	160	62	277	C ₁₄ H ₉ N ₂ OCl	11.1	10.9	
Me	5-Cl	3	3	160	68	292	C ₉ H ₇ N ₂ OCl	14.8	14.4	
Ph	5-Cl	4	7	180	60	279	C ₁₄ H ₉ N ₂ OCl	11.1	10.9	
Me	6-Cl	5	3	150	78	282-4	C ₉ H ₇ N ₂ OCl	14.2	14.4	5
Ph	6-Cl	6	7	185-90	66	294-5	C ₁₄ H ₉ N ₂ OCl	11.2	10.9	
<i>p</i> -NO ₂ .Ph	6-Cl	7	7	205-10	66	351-2	C ₁₄ H ₈ N ₃ O ₃ Cl	13.6	13.9	
<i>p</i> -OMe Ph	6-Cl	8	7	195	55	291-2	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	9.6	9.7	10
<i>o</i> -Cl. Ph.	6-Cl	9	10	180-85	*	220	C ₁₄ H ₈ N ₂ OCl ₂	9.9	9.6	
Me	7-Cl	10	3	160	79	262-3	C ₉ H ₇ N ₂ OCl	14.2	14.4	9
Ph	7-Cl	11	7	195-200	65	269**	C ₁₄ H ₉ N ₂ OCl	11.1	10.9	
<i>p</i> -NO ₂ .Ph	7-Cl	12	7	205-10	61	347-48	C ₁₄ H ₈ N ₃ O ₃ Cl	13.9	13.9	
<i>p</i> -OMe Ph	7-Cl	13	7	185-90	55	301-2	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	9.8	9.7	10
<i>o</i> -Cl. Ph.	7-Cl	14	10	185-90	*	239-40	C ₁₄ H ₈ N ₂ OCl ₂	9.4	9.6	

*Product formed on treating the reaction mass with hot dilute alkali.

**Melting point for this compound prepared by the 2-phenyl-7-chloro-3:1:4-benzoxazone-ammonia reaction followed by hot alkali treatment has been wrongly reported as 292°C.¹¹

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